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Influence Of Institutional Policy And Social Media On Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviours Among Senior Secondary School Students In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the influence of institutional policy and social media on adolescent heterosexual behaviors among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. It addresses two research questions and tests two hypotheses. A descriptive cross-sectional research design was employed for the study. The population consisted of all public senior secondary school students in the 2024/2025 academic year in Rivers State, totalling 185,225 students. A sample size of 400 was calculated using the Taro Yamane statistical formula. The researcher developed a structured questionnaire for data collection, which was administered to the respondents. The validity of the research instrument was ensured through face and content validation by two experts. Reliability was assessed using the split-half method, resulting in a reliability index of 0.91 for socio-demographic data and a prevalence index of 0.79 for heterosexual behaviour. Data analysis was carried out using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 and Microsoft Excel. Both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses (chi-square) were utilised to determine the relationship between the independent variable proxies. The findings regarding peer pressure and religious affiliation among adolescents are of significant public health importance, as they expose young people to potential risky outcomes in both the short and long term. The study concludes that having sufficient information does not guarantee the avoidance of sexual behaviour. Despite possessing knowledge about reproductive health, many adolescents engage in risky sexual behaviours, including kissing and sexual intercourse. This phenomenon can be attributed to various influencing factors, such as peer pressure and the pervasive impact of religious beliefs. Consequently, it is recommended that policymakers and curriculum planners prioritise the inclusion of sexuality education in both basic and secondary school curricula to foster positive attitudes, knowledge, and behaviours regarding sexuality among adolescents.

Keywords: Institutional policy and social media, adolescent, heterosexual, behaviours, senior secondary schools, and Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

On a global scale, the heterosexual behaviour of adolescents has become a significant topic of research, especially considering the rise of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Omorodion et al. (2021) and Kar et al. (2015), discussions surrounding adolescents' heterosexual behaviour have ignited moral and

policy debates, as anal and oral sex have gained popularity among this age group, with these behaviours increasing as they grow older. This is largely because adolescents represent a vital segment of society, and their health and sexual conduct can influence the future health and norms of the community. In Nigeria, individuals aged 10 to 24 represent approximately 31.4 per cent of the population. Adolescents do not form a uniform group; their requirements differ greatly based on factors such as age, gender, geographical region, socioeconomic status, and cultural background, among others. Their sexual and reproductive health requirements also vary significantly across different demographics, cultures, and religions. This variation can be attributed to the physiological and psychological transformations that lead them to seek sexual experiences and take risks. This delicate phase brings forth numerous challenges, particularly concerning sexual and reproductive health, as developmental changes occur within their bodies.

While adolescents have reached biological maturity and possess the ability to conceive, their sexual behaviours can lead to various long-term adverse effects. Additionally, adolescent girls who engage in risky sexual behaviours are more likely to encounter reproductive health issues, which can force them to face difficult choices, such as becoming teenage parents or opting for abortion. This reluctance to discuss sexuality openly often leads adolescent girls to rely on boys for information. Moreover, engaging in risk-taking sexual activities increases the likelihood for adolescents to contract sexually transmitted infections, including HIV/AIDS. If these young individuals do not seek prompt treatment for sexually transmitted infections, they may experience long-term health complications. Alongside these health risks, adolescent sexual behaviour can negatively impact academic performance; Lanari et al. (2020) noted that engaging in sexual activities often correlates with less participation in educational pursuits. The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) reported in 2019 that 80% of HIV infections among adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa occur in girls aged 15 to 19. Furthermore, adolescent girls and young women are also twice as likely to be living with HIV compared to their male counterparts of the same age, despite their having only one sexual partner and fewer instances of sexual encounters.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescents are expected to uphold values like chastity until marriage and follow parental guidance to avoid unhealthy sexual behaviours. However, many are sexually active, with the National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA) reporting around 1.9 million adults and 130,000 children under 15 living with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria. This highlights the need for targeted programs for youth, as many HIV cases are contracted during the teenage years.

In Rivers State, Nigeria, there is a rise in unplanned pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among adolescents, stemming from a lack of knowledge, protection, and guidance. Early sexual initiation and risky behaviours are common, worsened by limited access to comprehensive sexual education and socio-cultural barriers to open dialogue. Insufficient government initiatives and cultural norms may contribute to these issues, resulting in school dropouts among young girls due to pregnancies and the impact of HIV/AIDS.

Despite the increasing risky sexual behaviour among adolescents in Rivers State, empirical research on this topic is lacking in sub-Saharan Africa, with most studies focused on western Nigeria. Thus, the researcher aims to investigate the influence of institutional policy and social media on heterosexual behaviour among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to investigate the influence of institutional policy and social media on adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Determine the influence of institutional policy on heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
- ii. Assess the influence of social media on heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. To what extent does institutional policy influence heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
- ii. To what extent does social media influence heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses, which were tested at a 0.05 level of significance, guided the study.

- i. There is no significant relationship between institutional policy and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between social media and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Forms of Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviour

Sexual behaviour encompasses more than just sexual intercourse; it also includes actions like holding hands, kissing, and fondling. From holding hands to casual encounters, adolescents devote significant time to contemplating, discussing, and engaging in romantic relationships. The quality of these adolescent romantic connections can have lasting impacts on self-esteem and influence personal values about romance, intimate relationships, and sexuality (Mapalad & Psych, 2014). Approximately one in three 13-year-olds has experienced a romantic relationship, with the figure rising as they age: By 17, most adolescents have some experience with romantic partnerships. Typically, teens engage in multiple relationships throughout their teenage years, averaging around four. Nonetheless, cultural influences affect both the timing and quantity of these relationships. For instance, Asian American adolescents often enter romantic relationships later than their peers, as dating during adolescence is generally viewed less favourably in Asian cultures. Sexual minority youth encounter challenges in finding potential partners. Although many adolescents meet their romantic partners at school, sexual minority youth are less likely to find such social opportunities due to the discrimination they face and the limited number of openly LGBTQ peers.

Moreover, perceived social norms play a role in relationship quality. For instance, boys are more inclined to act as aggressive romantic partners if they believe their peers commonly exhibit aggression. Being friends with those who have had sexual experiences or who are older can increase a youth's likelihood of becoming sexually active; their sexual choices may be swayed by the expected approval or disapproval from their peers. The dangers associated with adolescent romantic relationships can be reduced by equipping young individuals with skills that foster healthy relationships. Young people who are sexually active within healthy relationships tend to engage in practices that lower their risk of teenage pregnancy and STDs, such as more consistent contraceptive use, greater transparency about their sexual histories, and increased sexual exclusivity (Weitzman et al., 2019). Furthermore, programs in schools and communities that help young people identify gender-based stereotypes, enhance conflict resolution and communication abilities, and diminish the acceptance of partner violence have been proven effective in decreasing dating violence among adolescents (Foshee et al., 2011).

Institutional Policy

Despite extensive research on what drives teenage sexual behaviour and contraceptive use, most studies have concentrated on individual traits and family backgrounds while overlooking community variables that policymakers can influence. Community attitudes and cultural practices significantly affect health outcomes. In certain contexts, these can encourage progressive and socially beneficial behaviours. However, particularly concerning adolescent sexual and reproductive health, many norms and traditions serve as obstacles rather than aids. These obstacles encompass widespread gender inequality, behaviours that support harmful customs like female genital mutilation (FGM), norms that permit violence against women and girls, taboos surrounding discussions about sexuality and reproduction, and attitudes that reject the provision of sexual education and reproductive health services. Addressing these entrenched

norms and traditions requires a coordinated approach grounded in a thorough understanding of the factors that drive them.

Moreover, laws and policies facilitate the delivery of health and social services to adolescents, mandate authorities to implement them, provide a framework for creating strategies and budgets, and reflect the stance of political leadership and the government on key issues. In some countries, supportive laws and policies, such as those mandating the provision of comprehensive sexuality education, exist, but they are more of an exception than the norm. Significant challenges include the lack of supportive laws; conflicting legislation, like a law requiring the ministry of health to provide contraceptive information and services to all individuals of reproductive age, being contradicted by another law that mandates parental consent for providing health services to minors; exceptions in laws, such as the ability to waive age-of-marriage laws under certain conditions; and restrictive legislation, such as limitations on access to safe abortion services. While legal and policy reform requires time and effort, its long-term benefits make it crucially important.

Comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) is a structured educational approach that covers the cognitive, emotional, physical, and social dimensions of sexuality. Its goal is to empower children and adolescents with knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that enhance their health, well-being, and sense of dignity, help them form respectful social and sexual relationships, and understand the impact of their choices on their well-being and that of others, while ensuring the protection of their rights throughout their lives (WHO, 2017; UNESCO, 2018). Additionally, it has been suggested that Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) offers young people essential information about their sexual health, which reduces misinformation and enhances their capacity to make informed and safe choices (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation, 2018; United Nations Population Fund, 2014). Research indicates that CSE is linked to a later onset of sexual activity, fewer sexual partners, increased use of condoms and contraceptives (UNESCO 2018), and advancing gender equality and rights (Vanwesenbeeck *et al.*, 2016).

The advantages of sexuality education are evident. Nonetheless, ongoing discussions continue over the effectiveness of various forms of sexuality education provided in diverse contexts. An 'abstinence-only' method emphasizes postponing sexual intercourse until marriage, whereas CSE adopts a more pragmatic and positive stance toward sexuality, providing youth with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to enjoy their sexuality (UNESCO 2018) by covering topics such as sexual pleasure, condom usage, and open discussions on sexual diversity (Ketting *et al.*, 2016; Peter *et al.*, 2015). It has been recognised that a fundamental requirement for the execution of sexuality education, whether comprehensive or abstinence-focused, is a solid policy and legislative framework, which is frequently absent in developing nations (Panchaud *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, school-based CSE has proven to be a cost-effective method for contributing to HIV prevention. Thus, state policies on sex education could be significant factors influencing adolescent sexual behaviour. Nevertheless, to postpone the commencement of sexual activity and prevent sexually transmitted infections, sexual health education should be provided to adolescents in senior secondary schools, along with fostering positive attitudes about gender and adolescent reproductive health norms during puberty, tailored to the social and cultural backdrop of Nigeria. As sexuality is often a delicate and taboo subject in many regions of Nigeria, it is seldom openly discussed by adolescents with their parents (Situmorang, 2016). This results in parents being somewhat conservative when conveying information related to sexuality to their offspring. Similarly, teachers often overlook the necessity of addressing sexuality education in a gender-neutral manner. Adolescent reproductive health is only addressed to a limited extent (Safitri, 2018).

Social Media

Mobile technologies, the internet, and social media have emerged as significant cultural phenomena, especially among young adults aged 18 to 29, often referred to as the Millennial generation. The frequency of social networking site usage among teenagers and young people has increased notably since 2006. Young people are actively engaged in numerous social activities, including sending daily messages to friends, posting bulletins, and participating in group and private messaging on these platforms.

According to Romo et al. (2017), social media (SM) and online communities play a crucial role in the lives of adolescents. Reports suggest that over 90% of adolescents across the nation have daily internet access and often go online multiple times throughout the day. Additionally, adolescents are heavy consumers of information disseminated by the media, leading to concerns about how media representations influence their sexual attitudes and societal expectations during a vital stage of development. While mass media and the internet offer valuable information about sexual health and positive sexual relationships for young individuals, numerous studies indicate that mass media can adversely affect teens' sexual behaviours.

Conversely, access to media and the internet enables adolescents to obtain information regarding their own and others' sexuality. Furthermore, the internet serves as a resource for adolescents to explore a variety of informational content on diverse topics that pique their interest, whether intentionally or accidentally. As a result, adolescents often visit pornographic websites driven by curiosity about the sexuality of the opposite sex or through chance encounters that lead them to these sites (Attwood et al., 2018; Harper & Hodgins, 2016; Lou et al., 2012). Scarcelli (2015) reported that male adolescents tend to access more pornography sites than their female peers. Additionally, sites featuring such content capture their interest, as most media present videos and images that enhance their curiosity and urge to experiment with what they have observed in real life (Chen et al., 2018; Donevan & Mattebo, 2017; Mattebo et al., 2014). Adolescents also utilise television as a source of information regarding sexual behaviours, which may lead to increased participation in various sexual activities (Vangeel et al., 2020; Vandenbosch & Eggermont, 2014). Moreover, online communication allows adolescents to explore their sexual interests, and the habits developed by these individuals can negatively influence their sexual behaviours and health, resulting in risks such as unprotected sex with casual partners (Rice et al., 2015). Behaviours formed during adolescence might have detrimental effects on the healthy progression of young people's sexual conduct. However, the impact of adolescents' relationship patterns, social networks, and the nature of their connections on risky sexual behaviours has not been thoroughly explored.

Consequences of Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviour

The initiation of sexual activity among adolescents remains an area of research interest for several reasons. Adolescents who refrain from sexual activity tend to perform better academically compared to those who are sexually active. Additionally, they avoid the concerns associated with unplanned teenage pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections. Moreover, when young people postpone engaging in sexual activity, they typically experience improved psychological well-being compared to those who do not. While positive romantic relationships can offer various benefits for young individuals, unhealthy ones present dangers that may have enduring consequences. Adolescents are especially prone to entering relationships that involve dating violence and risky sexual behaviours. Teenagers report experiencing dating abuse more frequently than individuals in any other age group.

Health Belief Model (Rosenstock & Becker, 1974)

Figure 2.2: The Health Belief Model

(Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Health_belief_model)

Developers of health belief model maintained that health-related behaviours are determined by whether the individuals perceive themselves to be susceptible to a particular health problem, see this problem as serious, are convinced that treatment or prevention activities are effective yet not costly in terms of money or effort or are exposed to a cue to take a health action. This model, according to Rosenstock and Becker (1974), focuses on the prevention of disease rather than its control. According to the model, the significant variables that influence the adoption of precautions against a perceived threat to health are a person's perceived vulnerability to the threat, the perceived severity of the threat and- benefit payoff that is associated with adopting preventive behaviours. This model is perhaps the largest lived paradigm that attempts to identify and critically evaluate the factors responsible for human behaviour as it relates to an individual's health. This model proposes that if one perceives himself as vulnerable or susceptible to, say, unwanted pregnancy or STIs, and feels that this is life threatening and may cost him his future and if he considers it more affordable to change his sexual behaviours or stop, the practice rather than die of STIs or ruin his future, the person is likely to adopt abstinence or a safer sexual behaviour. This theory, unlike the aforementioned ones, has stood the test of time. Following from the above, the present study was largely based on this model.

According to Brown et al. (1991), the Health Belief Model has been used to aid understanding in sexual risk-taking behaviour among various age and cultural groups (Lin et al., 2005). Several studies have examined the capacity of the Health Belief Model to predict whether sexually active adolescents and young adults will use protection against STIs during sexual or oral intercourse and found support for Health Belief Model in understanding safe sex behaviours (Brown et al., 1991; Laraque et al., 1997; Lin et al., 2005). Health Belief Model has been found to account for 43% of the variance in safe sex intentions in young adolescents (Petosa & Jackson, 1991). Furthermore, Downing-Matibag and Geisinger (2009) demonstrated that the Health Belief Model can serve as a useful framework for understanding sexual risk-taking during casual hookups, as adolescents' assessments of their own and peers' susceptibility to STIs are often misinformed and situational characteristics, such as spontaneity, undermine adolescents' sexual self-efficacy. Sequel to the above, the researcher posits that this theory

focuses on how an individual perceives him or herself to be susceptible to a particular health problem and, in turn, takes a health action in order not to be a victim. Thus, adopting this theory helps to understand in this study that any action taken by the adolescent towards heterosexual behaviour is based on the adolescent's perception of the health problem that may emanate from his or her action.

Asekun-Olarinmoye et al. (2014) examined the impact of mass media and the internet on the sexual behaviour of undergraduates in Osogbo metropolis, Southwestern Nigeria. In a descriptive cross-sectional study, 400 undergraduates were selected using a multistage random sampling technique. Out of 450 pretested semi-structured questionnaires distributed, 400 were returned properly completed. The data were analysed using SPSS statistical software version 16. The mean age of the respondents was 23.6 years (± 2.99). Most participants (95%) were aware of various forms of mass media. Approximately 64% of respondents spent 1 to 5 hours watching television daily, and many frequently used the Internet. About 38.3% and 24.2% of respondents cited the Internet and radio/television, respectively, as sources of information on sexual issues. Most respondents used the Internet for school assignments (83.0%, $n=332$), electronic mail (89.0%, $n=356$), and accessing sexually explicit materials (74.5%, $n=298$).

A majority of respondents (73.5%) believed that the Internet has a negative influence on youths' sexual behaviour, although 25.3% found accessing sexual material or movies acceptable. Of the 226 respondents who had ever had sex, 226 (100%) practised vaginal intercourse, 37 (16.4%) engaged in oral sex, 31 (13.7%) practised masturbation, and 10 (4.4%) participated in anal sex. Notably, 122 (54.0%) of respondents reported always using condoms, while 90 (40.0%) never used condoms during sexual activity, and 33 (14.6%) had engaged in sex with commercial sex workers. Further analysis showed that unmarried individuals were less likely to be sexually experienced compared to those who were married (adjusted odds ratio [AOR] = 0.075, 95% confidence interval [CI] = 0.008–0.679). Additionally, those who found accessing the Internet for sexual content unacceptable were also less likely to be sexually experienced than those who found it acceptable (AOR = 0.043, 95% CI = 0.016–0.122). Predictors of having multiple sexual partners included the respondent's sex and the frequency of Internet use, with females (AOR = 0.308, 95% CI = 0.113–0.843) and those who rarely used the Internet being less likely to have multiple partners. The study concluded that uncontrolled exposure to mass media and the Internet could negatively influence the sexual patterns and behaviours of youth.

Azuike and Nwabueze (2013) conducted a twelve-year review of adolescent sexual behaviour and practices in Nigeria. This article reviewed sexual practices and behaviours among Nigerian adolescents over twelve years, from January 2000 to December 2011. Publications from both local and international journals covering adolescent sexual behaviour and practices were retrieved from the NAUTH Medical Library. Results indicated that adolescents engage in unhealthy sexual behaviours characterised by early initiation of sexual activity, unsafe sex, and multiple sexual partners. Factors contributing to these behaviours include curiosity, peer influence, pleasure, and financial incentives.

Omeje et al. (2013) investigated environmental determinants of risky sexual behaviour among secondary school adolescents in the Obollo-Afor Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. The study involved 150 adolescent boys and girls from secondary schools, using a questionnaire for data collection. Mean scores and t-test statistics were employed for data analysis. Findings revealed that risky sexual behaviours among adolescents included watching pornographic films and pictures, engaging in sexual acts because others are doing so, and having unprotected sexual intercourse. Environmental factors identified included excessive alcohol consumption, associating with peers who engage in risky sexual behaviours, and exposure to inappropriate films. The results also indicated no significant difference in mean scores regarding risky sexual behaviour between male and female students.

Wang'eri and Habil (2013) explored the roles of family, peers, and protective factors related to sexual behaviour among urban adolescents in secondary schools in Mombasa County, Coast Province, Kenya. Data were collected through a paper-based questionnaire from 217 randomly selected students aged between 12 and 20 years from six secondary schools. The study revealed that moderate percentages of students engaged in various sexual behaviours. Few males and even fewer females reported having engaged in sexual intercourse. Across different socio-economic statuses, slightly higher percentages of respondents from the business class and families with unemployed parents reported engaging in sexual behaviours compared to those from other socio-economic categories. Parental monitoring appeared to be a protective factor, as few adolescents reported

engaging in sexual behaviours. The majority indicated that they did not experience peer pressure to engage in the sexual behaviours investigated.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilised to achieve the purpose of this study. The population of the study consisted of all public senior secondary school students in the 2024/2025 academic year in Rivers State with a total of one hundred and eighty-five thousand, two hundred and twenty-five (185,225) students. From the total population of 185,225 students, 400 sample size was generated using the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. One thousand two hundred (1200) students were randomly selected from twelve (12) LGAs across the three (3) Senatorial Districts. For the composition of respondents, a non-proportionate stratified random sampling technique was utilised to sample equal (100) respondents from each of the sampled schools, thereby arriving at 1200 respondents, which was used for the study. An adapted semi-structured closed-ended questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The data for this study were collected through the administration of a pre-designed, re-tested, semi-structured questionnaire to respondents. To ensure the validity of the research instrument (the questionnaire), there was an extensive literature review relating to the topic. Furthermore, to examine the evidence of the face and content validity, the instruments were validated by two experts. Split-half method was used for the reliability of the instrument. Fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire were administered to 50 students at the same time. Later, the questionnaires were numbered from 1 to 50. The even numbers were made to be group one (1) while odd numbers were made to be group two (2). Thereafter, the two groups of data were analysed using Kuder Richardson version 20 (Dichotomous options). The analysis revealed a reliability index of 0.91 for socio-demographic data, and prevalence of heterosexual behaviour was 0.79. The researcher employed three research assistants to assist in administering the questionnaires to the students in the selected schools. The items on the instrument were read out to them, and the respondents followed the instructions in completing the questionnaire. The data collection exercise lasted for four (4) months. The data analysis method for the study was descriptive statistical analyses. The data was computed and analysed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive and inferential (chi-square) statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between the proxies of the independent variable (institutional policy and social media) on the dependent variable (adolescent heterosexual behaviour).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does institutional policy influence adolescents’ heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Institutional policy and adolescents’ heterosexual behaviours

S.N		Frequency	Percent
1	Have you ever received lectures on sexuality in school?		
	No	336	28.0
	Yes	864	72.0
2	Have you ever heard of sexually transmitted infections (STIs)?		
	No	672	56.0
	Yes	528	44.0
3	During the school session, were you taught in any of the classes about STIs?		
	No	408	34.0
	Yes	792	66.0
4	During this school session, were you taught in any of the classes on how to avoid STIs?		
	No	336	28.0
	Yes	864	72.0
	Average		
	No	438	37
	Yes	762	64

Source: Field survey (2023): Key: 0-25% = Low; 26-50% = Moderate; 51-100% = High

Table 1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of institutional policy and adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings of the study showed that 72% of the respondents reported that they have received lectures on sexuality in school. However, only 44% of the respondents agreed that they have heard of sexually transmitted infections (STIs). On the other hand, 66% reported having received classes on STIs in the current school session while 72% indicated that they were taught on how to avoid STIs in the current school session.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does social media influence adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Social media as a determinant of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours

S.N		Frequency	Percent
1	I have used social media apps such as WhatsApp, Snapchat & Facebook to get information on sexual issues.		
	No	120	10.0
	Yes	1080	90.0
2	I have watched pornographic films and movies on the internet.		
	No	576	48.0
	Yes	624	52.0
3	I have used the internet to watch nude pictures of the opposite sex.		
	No	420	35.0
	Yes	780	65.0
4	The use of social media led me to get involved in video sex & sex chats.		
	No	420	35.0
	Yes	780	65.0
5	The use of social media has affected my sexual behaviour negatively.		
	No	288	24.0
	Yes	912	76.0
6	I feel addicted to the internet.		
	No	384	32.0
	Yes	816	68.0
	Average		
	No	368	31.0
	Yes	832	69.0

Source: Field survey (2023); **Key:** 0-25% = Low; 26-50% = Moderate; 51-100% = High

Table 2 displays the percentage distribution of social media influences on adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings of the study revealed that 90% of the students indicated that they have used social media apps such as WhatsApp, Snapchat & Facebook to get information on sexual issues. Furthermore, 52% of the respondents indicated that they have watched pornographic films and movies on the internet. 65% of the respondents indicated that they have used the internet to watch nude pictures of the opposite sex, which has also led them to get involved in video sex & sex chats. 76% of the respondents indicated that the use of social media has affected their sexual behaviour negatively, while 68% of the respondents feel addicted to the internet. Hence, based on the average (69%) responses of the study participants, we can deduce that social media influence on adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State is high.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between institutional policy and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 3: Chi-square analysis on significant relationship between institutional policy of parent/guardian and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State

Variable			Prevalence		Test Statistics
	No	Yes	No	Yes	
Institutional policy	No	F	270	178	$X_2(1)=86.093$
		%	22.5%	14.8%	
	Yes	F	247	505	P<.0001
		%	20.6%	42.1%	

Table 3 showed chi-square analysis on the relationship between institutional policy and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State. The study revealed a significant relationship between institutional policy and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours ($X_2=86.093$, $df= 1$, $p<05$). Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between institutional policy and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State, was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between social media and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 4: Chi-square analysis on significant relationship between social media of parent/guardian and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State

Variable			Prevalence		Test Statistics
	No	Yes	No	Yes	
Social media	No	F	205	178	$X_2(1)=25.011$
		%	17.1%	14.8%	
	Yes	F	312	505	P<.0001
		%	26.0%	42.1%	

Table 4 showed chi-square analysis on the relationship between social media and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State. The study revealed a significant relationship between social media and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours ($X_2=25.011$, $df=1$, $p<05$). Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between social media and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State, was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

First finding displays the frequency and percentage distribution of institutional policy and adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings of the study showed that 72% of the respondents reported that they have received lectures on sexuality in school. However, only 44% of the respondents agreed that they have heard of sexually transmitted infections (STIs). On the other hand, 66% reported having received classes on STIs in the current school session while 72% indicated that they were taught on how to avoid STIs in the current school session. Also, there is no significant relationship between institutional policy and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State. In line with the finding is the World Health Organisation (2020), which suggests that adolescents start having sexual relationships as early as 11 years. And therefore, parents, guardians, and health workers should start reproductive health education as early as possible, aimed at empowering children even before they turn 11 years. This also contributes to increasing teenage pregnancies, especially in Africa where about 14 million teenage pregnancies occur each year. It has also been estimated in sub-Saharan Africa that between 10% and 79% of all pregnancies in women below 20 years of age are described as unwanted.

Second finding displays the percentage distribution of social media influences on adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings of the study revealed that 90% of the students indicated that they have used social media apps such as WhatsApp, Snapchat & Facebook to get information on sexual issues. Furthermore, 52% of the respondents indicated that they have watched pornographic films and movies on the internet. 65% of the respondents indicated that they have used the internet to watch nude pictures of the opposite sex, which has also led them to get involved in video sex & sex chats. 76% of the respondents indicated that the use of social media has affected their sexual behaviour negatively, while 68% of the respondents feel addicted to the internet. Hence, based on the average (69%) responses of the study participants, we can deduce that social media influence on adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State is high. Also, there is no significant relationship between social media and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State. Supporting is Peter et al., (2015); Widman et al., (2014), Sedgh & Hussain, (2014) who posit that parents, health-care workers, and guardians should provide counselling to the youth regarding their choice of friendships. Parents should also start sex education early enough at home before teenagers get to learn issues of sex from their peers. Despite parents' knowledge on the importance of sex education, African parents see the practice as a difficult task due to cultural beliefs and norms. Thus, the early introduction of sexual education is perceived as detrimental rather than helping the adolescent to overcome sexual and reproductive health issues.

CONCLUSION

The study reveals that a significant number of adolescents possess knowledge about reproductive health, yet they still participate in risky sexual behaviours, including kissing and sexual intercourse. This phenomenon may be attributed to various influencing factors, such as institutional policy and the pervasive impact of social media. The findings emphasize the critical need for increased awareness and the implementation of community-based initiatives to address sexual health issues affecting adolescents. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of engaging the community in efforts to combat these challenges effectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Effective health education programs by school and health Agencies should target adolescents to improve knowledge on sexual issues, promote abstinence and motivate positive behaviours and minimise sexual risk.
2. Policy makers and curriculum planners should advocate for inclusion of sexuality education in basic and secondary school curriculum as a matter of priority to foster a positive attitude, knowledge and behaviour of adolescents towards sexuality.

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